

Our Vision

“Data and software as the scientific foundation for a sustainable energy future”

Motivation

Role of Research Software:

- Central to the analysis of complex data
- Generates new scientific insights

Importance in Energy Research:

- Crucial for simulation and modeling
- Manages and controls energy systems

Recognition of Research Software:

- Often not acknowledged as an independent research output
- Less valued compared to research data

Who is the RSE Community in Energy Research?

How do we strengthen the RSE Community in Energy Research?

Connecting & Collaborating

- Participating in RSE-focused conferences
- Engaging in NFDI section working groups

Building Knowledge & Tools

- Developing tools and workflows for RSE in energy research
- Sharing best practices and lessons learned

Hosting & Sharing

- Organizing workshops, conferences, and networking events
- Presenting keynotes and talks to spread RSE expertise

How do we engage with the RSE Community in Energy Research?

What can we do next?

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